
Analyze the Storage-Seats Located in the Rear Compartment of Ambulances Belonging to the Mobile Emergency Care Service (Samu) in the City of Bauru/Brazil

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ABSTRACT : Currently, ambulances are the most widely used means of transport for providing first aid in medical emergencies. They travel from the point of emergency to hospitals, transporting patients safely so that medical treatment can be carried out at the appropriate time. One of the problems occurring inside ambulances is the limited space during patient care. This can mainly interfere with the organization of materials and equipment, compromising the necessary agility of paramedics at the moment of the emergency. Thus, the objective of this work was to scientifically analyze the equipment storage compartment inside an ambulance in the SAMU (Mobile Emergency Care Service), to generate data for future projects in the sector. The methodology used to achieve the project's objective involved conducting research at the SAMU unit in the city of Bauru, using interviews with paramedics as basic tools. From this collected information, statistical interpretations were made of the acquired data, providing researchers with answers for a possible improvement in the working conditions of healthcare professionals and patient care. Therefore, this study reinforces that seemingly localized design interventions can produce significant systemic impacts in mobile emergency care services. Continued development of the proposed prototype is recommended, followed by field validation and potential incorporation of the improvements into future ambulance projects in the country.

KEYWORDS: Ambulance; “seat-chest”; Ergonomics; Paramedics; Design.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ambulances are the most widely used vehicles for delivering emergency medical care. They travel from the site of occurrence to hospitals, transporting patients safely so that treatment can be administered at the appropriate time. Ambulances are equipped with various emergency devices, such as ventilators, defibrillators, infusion pumps, among others, and rely on trained healthcare professionals capable of operating them effectively. All these devices are essential in emergency care by providing vital support to patients.

Hignett and Ferreira (2004) emphasized the importance of ergonomics in ambulances, noting the need for layouts that increase paramedic reach and minimize response time. Their study identified design priorities for ambulances: (1) facilitate cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR); (2) improve comfort and habitability; and (3) remove obstructions and standardize equipment location for easy access. Therefore, it is crucial that rescuers and paramedics master emergency equipment while working in an environment that supports safe and efficient performance, minimizes additional risks, and maintains public confidence in rescue operations.

The primary responsibility of healthcare professionals working inside ambulances lies in their ability to effectively manage adversities while delivering first aid. In this context, maximum efficiency is imperative due to the critical time sensitivity associated with life-saving situations. Any measure that contributes—even minimally—to accelerating this process is considered crucial for life preservation. Nystrom and Ahl (2006) described the importance of rapid response, highlighting the anxiety, fear, and loneliness experienced by patients until the arrival of mobile emergency care, followed by significant relief upon arrival. Ergonomic intervention in mobile emergency vehicles is therefore essential for three main reasons: (1) work effectiveness; (2) safety of individuals and equipment; and (3) professional comfort under demanding conditions.

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Significant physical injury challenges are faced by teams operating in mobile emergency medical services. While approximately 24% of non-emergency healthcare professionals may require long-term postural care, this percentage can reach 56% among emergency personnel, according to Doormaal et al. (1995). In a U.S. study by Maguire et al. (2002), the injury rate among these professionals was approximately 34.6% per year. Maguire and Smith (2013) further observed that between 2003 and 2007, injury rates among these professionals tripled compared with earlier U.S. national statistics.

Given this scenario, a critical problem was identified related to optimizing the ambulance work environment. The focus was to improve safety, effectiveness, and comfort for both healthcare professionals and patients. Currently, items stored in the under-seat compartments used during care are disorganized and lack dedicated divisions. This results in delays during emergency actions and increases the risk of injury due to the need for rapid searching among objects.

Brazilian Standard ABNT NBR 14561 establishes manufacturing requirements for emergency medical and rescue vehicles. Ambulance manufacturers must comply with this standard to ensure crew safety. Among its guidelines are the use of plastic or metallic materials in cargo compartments with appropriate surface coating, as well as stainless steel or anodized aluminum exterior hardware free of sharp edges to mitigate injury risks. The standard also requires that equipment supports be fully recessed to prevent dangerous displacement during transport.

According to Iida (2000), it is essential to ensure not only technical quality but also effective user interaction and product aesthetics. Efficient storage-seat design must consider principles such as equitable use, flexibility, simplicity, intuitiveness, and reduced physical effort. Comprehensive ergonomic analysis is vital to examine tasks, improve interfaces, and evaluate products through a participatory approach with users.

Comparisons between American ambulance designs and Brazilian storage practices indicate opportunities for improvement, according to the *Ambulance Patient Compartment Human Factors Design Guidebook* (2015). U.S. ambulances tend to emphasize accessibility, supply organization, and secure equipment fixation. In Brazil, these aspects still present opportunities for enhancement. The objective of this research was to analyze the storage-seats located in the rear compartment of ambulances from the Mobile Emergency Care Service (SAMU) in the city of Bauru. Following this analysis, potential improvements in internal organization could be evaluated in the future. The study also investigated whether the redesigned storage-seat would meet rescuers' expectations.

Figure 1 - Photographs of the trunk of a modern ambulance, located under the patient seats.

Source: Vanucci (2018)

The methodology employed in this research delved into the study of the layout of the storage compartment used inside ambulances. Thus, the relationships between the existing layout in SAMU ambulances and healthcare professionals were analyzed, as well as the benefits that a change in the internal design of an ambulance would bring to the routine of these professionals. To carry out these analyses, research was conducted at the SAMU unit in the city of Bauru, using interviews with paramedics who worked directly in mobile emergency care. From this collected information, statistical interpretations were performed on all the acquired data. Comparatively, in the method described in the article "Task Analysis of Paramedics in the Ambulance Patient Compartment" (2013) and in Vanucci (2018), interviews and questionnaires were conducted to evaluate performance and identify any complaints related to work in the ambulance. The results obtained were analyzed and, based on the collected data, it was possible to improve the quality of care provided.

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2 OBJECTIVES

2.1 Main Objective

The main objective of this research project was to analyze the storage-seats located in the rear compartment of ambulances belonging to the Mobile Emergency Care Service (SAMU) in the city of Bauru.

3 METHODOLOGY

Regarding the research procedure, the study was classified as a direct methodology. Concerning its objective, it was exploratory research aimed at improving understanding of the topic. The study involved bibliographic investigation and field research. The hypothetical-deductive method was adopted, in which the researcher formulated hypotheses and tested them through deductive processes.

The experimental methodology was divided into three (3) main stages (Figure 2).

- **Step 1:** bibliographic research to provide scientific grounding.
- **Step 2:** interviews with 10 SAMU rescuers from Bauru.
- **Step 3:** statistical analyses and ergonomic evaluation of the ambulance environment.
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Figure 2 – Methodology used in the research

Source: Authors

This study was conducted in full compliance with Brazilian National Health Council Resolution No. 466/2012 and the Plataforma Brasil procedures. The research was approved by the Research Ethics Committee under opinion number 4,729,155 (CAAE: 46549021.5.0000.0076). A research partnership was established with São Paulo State University (UNESP) and the University of São Paulo (USP - São Carlos), specifically the Center for Engineering Applied to Health (CEAS). Interviews were conducted at the SAMU unit in Bauru. A structured questionnaire containing 16 closed-ended questions was used. Respondents rated each item from 1 (worst/lowest intensity) to 10 (best/highest intensity). The list of questions is described below:

• List of questions applied to paramedics

- 1 – Rate the pain and discomfort paramedics experience from 1 to 10 while attending to patients inside the Ambulance.
- 2 - Rate the comfort of the reclining seat used inside the ambulance from 1 to 10.
- 2 - Rate the usefulness of the reclining seat used inside the ambulance from 1 to 10.
- 3 - Rate the safety of the reclining seat from 1 to 10.
- 4 - Rate the functionality of the seatbelt from 1 to 10.
- 5 - Rate the internal ergonomics of the ambulance models (Iveco, Fiat, Mercedes, etc.) in the department from 1 to 10.
- 6 - Rate the adaptability of the patient care equipment in the department's ambulances from 1 to 10.
- 7 - Rate the ease of access to the storage compartment located under the side seat of the ambulance on a scale of 1 to 10

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8 - Rate the danger of the storage compartment seat posing a risk of physical harm to the rescuer during handling on a scale of 1 to 10.

9 - Do you know anyone who has suffered physical harm while handling the storage compartment?

10 - What is your opinion on the need for a cushioning and protection system for opening the storage compartment located under the seat?

11 - Rate the organization of materials inside the storage compartment on a scale of 1 to 10.

12 - Rate the usefulness of the materials inside the storage compartment on a scale of 1 to 10.

13 - Rate the frequency of use of the materials inside the storage compartment on a scale of 1 to 10.

14 - Rate the ease of handling the storage compartment during emergency calls and operations on a scale of 1 to 10. 15 - Rate from 1 to 10 how easy it is to find materials inside the toolbox during calls and operations.

16 - Rate from 1 to 10 how necessary the first responders believe it is to install internal lighting and a panel indicating the presence of materials inside the toolbox.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Data Collection Results – Interviews with 10 SAMU Rescuers

During 2024, ten (10) rescuers from the SAMU unit in Bauru participated voluntarily. The sample included nurses, nursing technicians, nursing assistants, and driver-rescuers. Each volunteer in the interviews was numbered according to Table 1.

Table 1 - Relationship between Code/Individual/Profession		
Codes	Individual	Profession (Function)
S1	First responder 1	Nursing technician and nurse
S2	First responder 2	Nursing technician
S3	First responder 3	Nursing technician
S4	First responder 4	Nursing technician
S5	First responder 5	Nursing assistant
S6	First responder 6	Driver and nursing technician
S7	First responder 7	Nursing technician
S8	First responder 8	Driving and customer service assistant
S9	First responder 9	Nurse
S10	First responder 10	Nurse
Source: Authors		

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Table 2 shows demographic data for the studied sample, such as sex, age, marital status, height, weight, professional experience, and educational background.

Table 2 - Relationship between Code and Demographic Data							
First responders' code	Sex	Age	Marital status	Height (m)	Weight (kg)	Experience (Years)	Instruction
S1	F	44	Divorced	1,77	95	+ de 20	Higher education
S2	F	43	Stable Union	1,60	69	3-6 month	Higher education
S3	M	45	Married	1,83	99	+ de 20	Technical Training
S4	M	44	Divorced	1,89	116	9-20	Higher education
S5	M	66	Married	1,70	70	+ de 20	Secondary Education
S6	M	45	Single	1,87	98	3-6	Technical Training
S7	F	48	Widower	1,72	82	+ de 20	Incomplete higher education
S8	M	44	Married	1,82	95	9-20	Technical Training
S9	M	53	Married	1,81	99	+ de 20	Higher education
S10	M	42	Married	1,78	79	3-6	Higher education

Source: Authors

4.2 Information About the Interviewees

The professions of those interviewed during the research were as follows: nurse, nursing technician, nursing assistant, and ambulance driver. When analyzing the number of interviewees at the Mobile Emergency Care Service Unit (SAMU) in Bauru, it was found that nursing technicians were the most frequently interviewed professionals. Half of the participants had more than 20 years of experience, while the remainder ranged from 3 months to 20 years. The sample consisted of 70% males and 30% females. The mean height of the sample was 1.778 m, which is above the Brazilian adult average of approximately 1.665 m, indicating that the studied group is taller than the national average.

Figura 3 - Graph showing the professional activities of the respondents.

Source: Authors

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Among these professionals interviewed, 50% had more than 20 years of experience, and the other 50% were divided between 3-6 years, 9-20 years, and 3-6 months of experience. An analysis of the marital status profile of the interviewees showed that 50% of the interviewees were married, and the other 50% were distributed among divorced, in a stable union, widowed, and single. For the age range of the interviewees, when comparing the number of male and female individuals by age range, in the sample of 10 individuals analyzed in this research, it was found that the male individuals were in the age range of 42 to 66 years, and the female individuals studied were in the age range of 43 to 48 years.

The first part of the sociodemographic results studied the characterization of the sample through the variable biological sex. Ten individuals were analyzed, and it was found that 30% were female and 70% were male. The female participants worked as nurses and nursing technicians. The male participants worked as nurses, nursing technicians, nursing assistants, and drivers. The anthropometric data of the interviewees can be seen in Table 6. It contains a demonstrative figure with the basic body parts of the individual, such as height, etc. (Table 3).

Code	1- Height from head to hip	2- Popliteal height	3- Buttock / Patella	4- Shoulder-to-elbow distance	5- Forearm-hand distance	6- Stature	7- Hip	8- Waist	9- Distance Between Shoulders
S1	82	58	58	51	49	1,77	35	41	45
S2	81	59	51	36	43	1,60	38	30	39
S3	90	55	57	28	45	1,83	48	38	44
S4	55	58	64	53	45	1,89	66	45	47
S5	81	58	57	43	42	1,70	36	33	46
S6	74	63	62	40	46	1,87	43	41	50
S7	59	50	50	38	41	1,70	43	34	44
S8	89	61	57	38	41	1,82	40	34	46
S9	90	54	56	40	45	1,81	52	44	49
S10	90	58	60	45	46	1,79	39	33	42
Average	79,1	57,4	57,2	41,2	44,3	1,778	44	37,3	45,2
statistical mode	90	58	57	40	45	-	43	41	44

Source: Authors

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After analyzing the heights of the individuals interviewed, it was observed that the sample average was 1.778 m. Comparing this with the general average height of Brazilian adults, which is approximately 1.665 m, it was noted that our sample is above average, indicating that the interviewed participants are, on average, taller than the adult population of the country.

4.3 Results of the Questionnaire Applied to the Rescuers

The graph in Figure 4 shows that most rescuers rated the discomforts inside the ambulance as mild, concentrating on scores of 1 (50%) and 3 (30%). Only one specific case assigned a high score, 8 (10%). These data indicate that the discomforts, in general, are of low intensity, although there are isolated situations that require attention to reduce occupational risks. Some examples of pain reported by the rescuers interviewed were in the lower back, knee, shoulder, muscle pain, and left arm.

Figure 4 – Scores from 1 to 10 regarding the pain and discomfort that first responders feel while attending to patients inside the ambulance. (N = Scores assigned, Q = Number of respondents); Score 10 = maximum pain; Score 1 = no pain

Source: Authors

For the analysis of figure 6, it was necessary to present the seat from figure 5, which was used in the rescuer interviews.

Figure 5: “seat-chest” or Trunk Ambulance Seat for the rescuers (TASR)

Source: Authors

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Figure 6 - Score assigned from 1 to 10 regarding seat comfort in Figure 5. (Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

Analysis of Figure 6 shows that most respondents rated the seat comfort with median scores, with a score of 7 being the most frequent (30%), followed by a score of 5 (20%). 20% of first responders gave very low scores (1 and 3) while 20% gave very high scores (9 and 10), indicating that there are quite disparate opinions. The concentration of votes was in the average, indicating that although the seat is in reasonable condition, it can be improved to better meet the comfort expectations of most users.

Figure 7 – Rating attributes from 1 to 10 regarding the usefulness of the seat in Figure 16. (N = Ratings assigned, Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

According to Figure 7, the graph indicates that the perception of the seat's usefulness is highly positive: 90% of respondents gave scores between 7 and 10, and only one isolated case (10%) gave a low score (3). This demonstrates that, for most, the seat is of great importance to their work routine.

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Figure 8 – Scores from 1 to 10 regarding the safety of the seat in Figure 5. (N = Scores assigned, Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

Figure 8 reveals divided perceptions about the safety of the seat: while some rescuers assigned high scores (7, 8, 9, and 10, totaling 70%), indicating confidence, others rated it 1 (20%), demonstrating a feeling of insecurity. Thus, the data point to polarized opinions, suggesting the need for improvements to increase the reliability of the seat.

Figure 9 - Graph of the rating from 1 to 10 regarding the functionality of the seat belt in Figure 5.

Source: Authors

Regarding Figure 9, it is shown that most rescuers positively evaluated the functionality of the seat belt, with the most notable scores being 10 (40%) and 9 (20%). However, there were records of intermediate scores (3 to 6, each with 10%), indicating that there is not overall satisfaction with the equipment. The existence of some flaws in the seat belt system reinforces the need for adjustments. Some of the suggestions for improvements to the seats located on top of the trunk were: (1) 3-point seat belt; (2) improved quality of the seat belts; (3) more comfortable seats; (4) reduction in the number and increase in the width of the seats.

Most rescuers rated the internal ergonomics of the ambulances as intermediate, with 70% assigning a score of 7 (Figure 10). The remaining responses were distributed in isolated scores, such as 6, 8, and 10 (10% each). These data indicate a generally satisfactory perception regarding ergonomics, although there are still aspects that can be improved to achieve higher levels of comfort and suitability. Reports from paramedics showed dissatisfaction among staff regarding some ambulance brands, such as Mercedes-Benz, due to their narrower seating space hindering agility in the workplace, and a preference for the Ford Transit brand.

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Figure 10 – Scores from 1 to 10 regarding the internal ergonomics of ambulance models (Iveco, Fiat, Mercedes, etc.) used by SAMU in Bauru. (N = Scores assigned, Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

Figure 11 - Scores from 1 to 10 regarding the suitability of existing patient care equipment in the department's ambulances. (Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

According to Figure 11, the varying evaluations of the adaptation of ambulance equipment can be seen. The highest concentration occurred at score 7 (30%), indicating a predominantly positive perception, followed by scores 4 and 9 (20% each). There were also records of intermediate and high scores, such as 6, 8, and 10 (10% each). These results reveal that, although most consider the adaptation satisfactory, there are still divergences among the paramedics, suggesting a need for adjustments to better meet the different emergency situations.

Figure 12 - Scores from 1 to 10 regarding the ease of access to the storage compartment located under the side seat of the ambulance. (N = Scores assigned, Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

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According to the data in Figure 12, it can be seen that most rescuers positively evaluated the ease of access to the trunk, with 40% assigning a score of 10 and 20% a score of 7. However, there were also records of lower scores, such as 4 (20%) and 5 (10%), indicating that some professionals still encounter difficulties. Thus, it is concluded that access to the compartment is considered, in general, satisfactory, but presents points that can be improved to ensure greater practicality in its use.

Regarding the danger that the (TASR) can pose to first responders during its handling, Figure 13 shows some quite divergent assessments. While 30% assigned a score of 1, indicating that they perceive no risk, another 30% gave a score of 10, demonstrating a perception of high danger. In addition, there were responses distributed in intermediate values, such as 2, 6, 7, and 9 (10% each). These results reveal polarized opinions, suggesting that the experience of use varies among professionals and that it is necessary to investigate the factors that lead to such differences in order to reduce potential risks.

Figure 13 - Scores from 1 to 10 regarding the danger that the TASR in causing physical harm to the rescuer during its handling. (Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

Figura 14- Graph showing the number of acquaintances who have suffered physical harm while handling the TASR

Source: Authors

As shown in Figure 14, 30% of first responders stated that they knew someone who had suffered physical harm while handling the TASR, while 70% reported not knowing of any similar cases. This data indicates that, although most do not have direct contact with accident reports, a significant portion has witnessed or become aware of such occurrences, reinforcing the need for attention to this potential risk.

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Figure 15 - Rescuers' opinion on the need for a damping and protection system for opening the storage compartment located under the seat.

Source: Authors

According to Figure 15, the majority of first responders (80%) do not consider the implementation of a damping and protection system for opening the storage compartment located under the seat to be necessary, while 20% believe that such a feature should exist. These data indicate that, although most do not perceive a significant risk, a portion sees the need for improvements to increase safety in the use of the compartment, as they have likely witnessed an incident.

Figure 16 - Rating from 1 to 10 regarding the organization of materials inside the TASR (N = Ratings given, Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

The evaluation of the organization of materials in the TASR showed a wide range of responses, with scores of 5 and 8 standing out, both given by 20% of participants. The remaining scores were distributed at 10% each, except for 2 and 4, which were not chosen. This diversity highlights the lack of consensus among users, suggesting that, although some recognize a satisfactory organization, there are still areas for improvement. It is concluded, therefore, that it is necessary to adopt strategies for standardization and improvement in the arrangement of materials in order to provide a more uniform and positive experience.

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Figure 17 - Ratings from 1 to 10 regarding the usefulness of the materials inside the TASR (N = Ratings given, Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

The perception of the usefulness of the materials found inside the chest was very positively evaluated, indicating that all first responders believe that the existing equipment is widely used and important in all the care provided, with 70% rating it with the highest score and the other 30% distributed between scores of 8 and 9 (Figure 17).

Regarding the frequency of use of the materials, 40% of respondents say that the stored materials are part of their work routine, while 50% rated them between 5 and 8, and a portion of 10% reported a score of 3, indicating little use. The conclusion that can be reached is that although there are specific experiences in which the materials are rarely used, in most cases, the materials are part of the routine (Figure 18).

Figure 18 - Scores from 1 to 10 regarding the frequency of use of the materials inside the chest. (N = Scores assigned, Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

Figure 19 - Scores from 1 to 10 regarding the ease of handling the chest during service and operations. (N = Scores assigned, Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

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As shown in Figure 19, it can be seen that most users rate the handling of the trunk positively, with 70% of the scores between 7 and 10. However, the presence of low scores (1 and 4) indicates that there are still areas for improvement to ensure greater uniformity in satisfaction.

Most of the ratings are concentrated between scores of 6 and 10 (70%), indicating a predominantly positive perception of the internal organization of the trunk. However, the presence of low scores (2 and 4, totaling 20%) indicates that there are still some specific difficulties, suggesting a need for adjustments for greater standardization and efficiency in accessing the materials.

Figure 20 - Scores from 1 to 10 regarding the ease of finding materials inside the TASR during service calls and operations. (Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

Figure 21 - Scores from 1 to 10, indicating how necessary the rescuers believe the installation of interior lighting and the installation of a panel to indicate the presence of materials inside the cargo hold to be. (N = Scores assigned, Q = Number of voters)

Source: Authors

Opinions are divided: while 40% gave it a score of 1, indicating a low need for the installation, another 50% gave scores between 6 and 10, suggesting the feature's relevance to some of the evaluators. Thus, it is concluded that the measure may be beneficial, but it is not unanimously considered essential, highlighting divergences in user perception. Rescuers reported that there are few or no problems between the cargo box and the staff, and one believes that the splints located inside the cargo box could be placed in a more accessible location. No interviewee believes that any other ambulance equipment should be inside the cargo box, and none believe that the current opening method is complex and requires excessive force.

7 CONCLUSION

The present study achieved its main objective by critically analyzing the storage-seat ("seat-chest" or TASR) used in ambulances of the Serviço de Atendimento Móvel de Urgência (SAMU) in Bauru, identifying strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities for improvement from ergonomic and organizational perspectives. The investigation confirmed that, although the current system

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demonstrates satisfactory performance in several aspects, relevant gaps remain that justify redesign interventions aimed at optimizing the working environment of emergency responders.

Overall, the results indicate that professionals perceive the storage-seat as useful and functional for operational routines, with predominantly positive evaluations regarding utility, frequency of material use, and ease of access. These findings suggest that the compartment concept is appropriate and fulfills an important role in supporting pre-hospital care. However, the presence of moderate and dispersed evaluations in items such as comfort, perceived safety, and internal organization reveals that current performance still falls short of the ideal ergonomic standard.

One of the most relevant observations was the heterogeneity of responses. In several aspects—especially seat safety, risk of physical harm, and material organization—there was strong polarization among participants. This variability suggests that the user experience is not uniform among responders, possibly influenced by anthropometric differences, years of experience, ambulance make/model, and individual organizational practices. This finding reinforces the need for more universal design solutions aligned with user-centered ergonomics principles.

Although most respondents reported low levels of pain and discomfort during service, isolated reports of lower back, shoulder, and knee pain should not be overlooked. Considering the literature indicating a high incidence of occupational injuries in mobile emergency services, even sporadic occurrences must be addressed preventively. Therefore, ergonomic improvements to both the seat and chest access may act as risk mitigation measures in the medium and long term.

Another important finding concerns the internal organization of the “seat chest”. While some professionals considered the current arrangement acceptable, the dispersion of scores and qualitative suggestions indicates the absence of effective standardization. In emergency environments, where seconds are critical, any difficulty in locating materials represents a potential negative impact on patient response. Consequently, compartmentalized reorganization with clear visual identification and a usage logic based on item frequency appears to be one of the interventions with the greatest potential for operational gain.

Regarding mechanical safety, the data reveal that the current system is not widely perceived as dangerous; however, a non-negligible portion of users identifies risks or is aware of injury cases associated with handling. This result is particularly relevant from a safety engineering perspective: even low-frequency risks must be treated preventively in critical-use equipment. Thus, solutions such as damped opening mechanisms, elimination of pinch points, and improved hardware remain technically justified.

Anthropometric analysis showed that the sample has an average height above the Brazilian population mean, reinforcing the importance of considering a broad percentile range in ergonomic design. A design based solely on average dimensions may not adequately serve users at anthropometric extremes. Therefore, it is recommended that the new storage-seat project incorporate dimensional adjustability principles, optimized reach zones, and clearance margins compatible with population variability.

From a methodological standpoint, the study proved appropriate as an applied exploratory investigation, combining literature review, field research, and statistical analysis. However, some limitations must be acknowledged. The small sample size ($n = 10$) restricts the generalization of results to the entire SAMU system or other regions. In addition, the predominance of subjective responses may introduce perceptual bias. Future studies with larger samples, objective biomechanical measurements, and usability testing using physical prototypes may further deepen and validate the findings presented here.

Despite these limitations, the work offers a relevant contribution to health engineering and to the design of emergency vehicles in the Brazilian context. The study demonstrates that relatively localized improvements—such as internal reorganization, ergonomic seat adjustments, enhancement of the opening system, and possible signaling and lighting features—have the potential to increase operational efficiency, reduce occupational risks, and improve team comfort.

In summary, the storage-seat currently used in the analyzed ambulances fulfills its basic function but presents clear opportunities for ergonomic and functional optimization. The implementation of a new design, grounded in real-world usage data and user-centered ergonomics principles, is likely to contribute to:

- faster material location;
- reduction of occupational injury risks;
- increased comfort and perceived safety;
- operational standardization of the internal environment;
- indirect improvement in patient care quality.

Therefore, this study reinforces that seemingly localized design interventions can produce significant systemic impacts in mobile emergency care services. Continued development of the proposed prototype is recommended, followed by field validation and potential incorporation of the improvements into future ambulance projects in the country.

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